

A CLINICAL STUDY OF PERINATAL AND MATERNAL MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY IN GESTATIONAL HYPERTENSION, PREECLAMPSIA AND ECLAMPSIA

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Abstract

In India, hypertensive disorders complicating pregnancy are common and continue to be responsible for the largest proportion of perinatal deaths resulting from prematurity and IUGR and are major contributors to perinatal and maternal morbidity and mortality.

The aim: The present study is undertaken to analyse the cases of preeclampsia and eclampsia, including consequences concerning preterm delivery, IUGR, IUD and stillbirth and for the evaluation of a safe motherhood program at the population level.

Materials and methods: The present study was conducted on 105 selected cases from the census (sample of 12,589 patients) of pregnancy-induced hypertension (gestational hypertension, preeclampsia and eclampsia).

Results: Hypertensive cases complicating pregnancy of the foetal deliveries conducted during the study period, out of which Gestational hypertension (GTN) cases reported were 44. Preeclampsia (PE) cases were 39, severe preeclampsia (SPE) were 1 and Eclampsia cases were 21. Labetalol alone was used in 62 cases, and 44 babies were born without any complications. As an anticonvulsant magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄, 7H₂O) was used in all cases of imminent eclampsia and eclampsia (MgSO₄ PRITCHARD Regime) in a total number of 38 cases. Preterm/prematurity was the most common cause of perinatal death. The total number of NICU admissions was 42 (40 %).

Conclusions: The early use of anti-hypertensive drugs, the optimum timing of delivery, strict fluid balance, and anticonvulsants in cases of eclampsia will help to achieve a successful outcome. Early transfer to a specialist centre is important, and the referral centres should be well-equipped to treat critically ill patients.

Keywords: gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, preterm, prematurity, perinatal death, intrauterine death, neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), labetalol, magnesium sulphate, hypertensive disorders.

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1. Introduction

Hypertensive disorders are the most common medical complication occurring in 12–22 % of all pregnancies. Eclampsia is the presence of a new onset seizure in a woman with preeclampsia. 44 % of the seizures occur postnatally, 38 % occur antepartum and 18 % in the intrapartum period [1, 2].

The Path physiology of preeclampsia is poorly understood; it is also described in pregnancies where there is trophoblast but no foetal tissue (Complete Molar Pregnancies in Goldstone and Berkowitz, 1994). The pathological hallmark of preeclampsia appears to be a failure of the second wave of trophoblast invasion. From 8–18 weeks of gestation, that is responsible for the destruction of muscular layers of spiral arterioles as such establishment of definitive uteroplacental circulation. As pregnancy progresses, the metabolic demands of the foetus's placental unit increase and spiral

arterioles cannot accommodate the increase in blood flow. This leads to the development for want of a more precise term, «Placental Dysfunction», which manifests clinically as preeclampsia.

A Recent publication suggested that soluble FMS like Tyrosine Kinase (SFLT1) antagonist of VEGF and Placental growth factor is an exclusive toxemia factor released from placenta leading to widespread Vasospasm and endothelial injury, which is a clinical hallmark of preeclampsia although attractive, this hypothesis needs to be validated.

Preeclampsia is a leading cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide [2]. Clinical studies of preeclampsia and eclampsia can be used to evaluate safe motherhood programs at the population level. Despite recent advances in detection and Management, Preeclampsia remains the most common cause of maternal death in the USA, accounting for approximately 15 % of all maternal deaths. It is estimated that eclampsia is a factor of up to 10 % of maternal deaths in developed countries and probably accounts for 50,000 maternal deaths per year worldwide. In developing countries, however, it is around 6–7 % as per WHO, 1998. However, occurrence rates are highest among nulliparous women from lower socio-economic backgrounds, teenagers and women who have crossed 35 years [3].

The purpose of the present study is to know the incidence and consequences of preeclampsia and eclampsia in relation to preterm delivery, IUGR, IUD and stillbirth and early neonatal death and also the evaluation of safe motherhood programs at the population level and the study on Perinatal and maternal mortality and morbidity ratios.

The aim of the research: The present study is undertaken to analyse the cases of preeclampsia and eclampsia, including consequences concerning preterm delivery, IUGR, IUD and stillbirth and for the evaluation of a safe motherhood program at the population level.

2. Materials and methods

The Present study was carried out on 105 cases of pregnancy-induced hypertension (i.e. Gestational Hypertension, Preeclampsia and eclampsia) admitted to RIMS Hospital, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, from December 2013 to March 31st, 2016 were considered in the present study.

Bioethics: Institutional clearance and ethical consent were obtained (Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Kadapa, dated 29/11/2013, REG NO: M137214141.

Inclusion criteria

– Patients beyond 20 weeks of pregnancy with hypertensive disorders complicating pregnancy are admitted to RIMS Hospital.

– All patients with hypertension, proteinuria, and convulsions beyond 20 weeks were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

– All pregnant patients with hypertensive disorders complicating pregnancy getting terminated before 28 weeks were excluded.

– All chronic hypertension cases were excluded from the study.

Both booked, un-booked and booked elsewhere (from Private medical practitioners) and all patients who were diagnosed to have hypertension complicating pregnancy were admitted to RIMS Hospital were studied. All patients were in the third trimester of pregnancy.

The patients were selected irrespective of parity, consanguinity and from all socio-economic classes. The Proforma noted detailed history, period of gestation, last menstrual period and expected date of delivery, history of previous pregnancies, and results of the present study. Ethical commission permission has been sought regarding the collection of data from patients. General nursing care, fluid and electrolyte balance were maintained, and urine output was monitored with an indwelling catheter.

Management protocol is followed in RIMS Hospital and used for this study.

1) At OPD:

Blood pressure checked → if $\geq 140/90$ mmHg → Repeat after 4 hours → Normal → Regular ANC's.

↓

2) Persistent value $\geq 140/90$ mmHg.

⇓

3) Send for urine Albumin ⇒ Negative ⇒ Regular ANC.

⇓

Positive.

⇓

4) Send PIH profile.

(Blood urea, serum creatinine, uric acid, platelet count, peripheral smear, LDH, bilirubin, Albumin, A/G ratio, SGOT, SGPT).

5) If any of the values are abnormal, hospitalise the patient.

6) Determine the gestation age:

If gestation age > 37 weeks:

– Delivery is the rule.

If gestation age < 37 weeks:

– Diastolic BP 90-100 mmHg – Observation, urine albumin (alternate day), BP chart fourth hourly.

– Diastolic BP \geq 100 mmHg ⇒ Anti-hypertensive to be started Tab Labetalol 100mg – BD.

– Urine albumin (alternate day).

– Once the BP is under control, discharge the patient.

– Follow up:

1) every week with NST, USG.

2) Check blood pressure, urine albumin.

Statistics Methods

Raw data were entered into a Microsoft excel spreadsheet. Appropriate statistical tests were done using SPSS 17A and openepi.com to compare qualitative and quantitative data. The qualitative data were presented in the form of numbers and percentages, and the quantitative data were presented in the form of mean and standard deviation.

3. Results

Eclampsia, preeclampsia, severe preeclampsia (SPE) and gestational hypertension (GTN) cases, out of 105 cases were:

– Gestational hypertension (GTN) cases were – 44.

– Preeclampsia (PE) cases were – 39.

– Severe preeclampsia (SPE) cases were – 1.

– Eclampsia cases were – 21.

In the present study, the total number of cases selected was – 105.

– The total number of gestational hypertension cases was – 44 (41.90 %).

– The total number of preeclampsia cases was – 39 (37.14 %).

– Severe preeclampsia was – 1 (0.95 %).

– The total numbers of eclampsia cases were – 21 (20 %) (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1. Different types of Pregnancy disorders

- The maximum number of cases in the age group of 22–25 years is 42 (40 %)
- The minimum number of cases in the age group of 38+ years is 1 (0.95 %).
- Maximum cases were booked cases were 76 (72.38 %), and unbooked cases were – 29 (27.61 %).
- The ratio of booked cases to unbooked cases was 2.62:1.
- In this study majority of the patients were from low socio-economic status, i.e., 72 cases (68.6 %) than middle class 33 (31.43 %).
- The number of cases in the primi gravida group, i.e., 51 (48.58 %) and Multigravida group account for 54 (51.42 %).
- In this study, the total number of EMLSCS deliveries was – 65 (66.68 %), and outlet for-
cipes deliveries were – 4 (3.80 %) (**Table 1**).

Table 1
Distribution of cases according to the Age Group

Age groups in years	Number of cases	Percentages
18–21	28	26.7
22–25	42	40
26–29	15	14.3
30–33	13	12.4
34–37	6	5.7
38–41	1	0.9
Total	105	100
Case type		
Booked	76	72.4
Unbooked	29	27.6
Socio economic status		
Middle	33	31.4
Lower	72	68.6
Parity		
Multi	54	51.4
Primi	51	48.6
Gestational age in weeks		
28–32	14	13.33
33–36	17	16.19
37–41	74	70.5
Mode of delivery		
EMLSCS	65	66.6
Induction	29	27.6
Not delivered	1	0.9
NVD	5	4.76
Outlet forceps	4	3.8
VBAC	1	0.9

- **The maximum** number of cases had systolic blood pressure in the range of 140–160 mmHg, i.e., 84 cases (80 %).
- **The maximum** number of cases had diastolic blood pressure in the range of 90–100 mmHg, i.e., 82 cases (78.09 %) (**Table 2**).

Table 2
Vital parameters and investigations in the present study

Systolic blood pressure (SBP) in mm Hg	Number of cases	Total (%)
<140	4	3.81
140–160	84	80
>160	17	16.19
Diastolic blood pressure		
<90	1	0.95
90–100	83	–
101–110	14	–
111–120	6	–
>120	2	–
Urine albumin (dipstick)		
1+	12	11.4
2+	44	41.9
3+	1	0.95
Nil	44	41.9
Trace	4	3.82
LFT		
Nil	102	97.2
Raised	3	2.8
RFT		
Nil	105	–
Platelet count		
Decreased	9	8.57
Normal	96	91.4

- The number of patients in whom tab. Labetalol (L) was used were – 62 (59.05 %).
- The number of patients in whom Labetalol plus MgSO₄ (LM) were used:36 cases (34.30 %).
- The total number of cases where MgSO₄ Plus Nifedipine(MN) was used: 2 and Nifedipine(N) was: 3, with tab: Labetalol plus Nifedipine(LN) was: 1 (**Table 3**).

Table 3
Method of Treatment

Method of Treatment	Number of cases	Total(%)
Labetalol (L)	62	59
Labetalol+MgSO ₄ (LM)	36	34
Labetalol+Nifedipine (MN)	1	0.9
MgSO ₄ with Nifedipine (MN)	2	1.9
Nifedipine (N)	3	2.85
No Treatment	1	0.95

- In this study maximum number of cases had an Apgar score of ‘8’ in one minute – 50 cases (47.62 %) followed by an Apgar score of 6, i.e., 28 cases (26.67 %)
- Apgar score of Not Applicable(i.e. IUD with Stillbirths) in 17 cases, i.e., (16.19 %).

- In the Apgar score in 5 min, maximum cases were in the group of Apgar score of 10–50 cases (47.61 %) followed by in the group of ‘8’ – 28 cases (26.67 %).
- Apgar score of Not Applicable(i.e. IUD with stillbirths) in 17 cases amounts to (16.19 %).
- A maximum number of cases were in the group 2.5–3.0 kg, i.e., 32 cases (30.47 %) and the minimum in the group <1.0 kg is one case (0.95 %) (**Table 4**).

Table 4
Neonatal parameters at birth

APGAR at 1 min	Number of cases	Percentages
2	5	4.7
4	5	4.7
6	28	26.7
8	50	47.6
NA (IUD plus Still Birth)	17	16.19
APGAR at 5 min		
4	5	4.7
6	5	4.7
8	28	26.7
10	50	47.6
NA	17	16.19
Birth weight in kgs		
<1	1	0.9
1–1.5	13	12.4
1.5–2	18	17.14
2–2.5	19	18.1
2.5–3.0	32	30.4
3.0–4.0	7	9.5
>4	3	2.85
NA (IUD Plus Still Birth)	1	0.9

- In this study, the maximum foetal complication was IUGR – 29 cases (27.62 %) (**Table 5**)

Table 5
Showing Fetal complications

Foetal complications	Eclampsia	GTN	Preeclampsia	SPE	Total
Hypoxia	1	2	6		9
IUGR	8	8	13		29
MAS	2	2	2		6
Normal	10	32	18	1	61
Total number of cases	21	44	39	1	105

- Post-partum eclampsia was seen only in 1 case, and post-partum haemorrhage was seen in 4 cases.
- Abruptio – 7 cases.
- HELLP Syndrome with 9 cases and DIC in 1 case (**Table 6**).

Table 6
Showing maternal complications

Maternal complications	Booked	Unbooked	Total
Abruption	4	3	7
HELP	5	4	9
Normal	63	19	82
PPE	1	–	1
PPH	3	1	4
Pulmonary oedema	–	1	1
DIC	–	1	1
Total number of cases	76	29	105

– Maximum babies were term babies, 74 (70.47 %) and preterm babies, 30 (28.57 %) (Table 7).

Table 7
Distribution of Eclampsia, Preeclampsia, SPE and GTN according to maturity

Maturity	Eclampsia	GTN	Preeclampsia	SPE	Total	Total (%)
Preterm	6	9	15		31	29.6
Term	14	35	24	1	74	70.4
Total Cases	21	44	39	1	105	100

- The total number of babies born alive was – 86 (82).
- The total number of babies born dead was – 15 (14.28 %).
- In this study, 42 babies (40 %) needed NICU admission (Table 8).

Table 8
Showing babies' morbidity and mortality

NICU admission	Number of cases	Total (%)
NA	2	1.91
No	61	58.1
Yes	42	40
Mortality	Number of cases	Total (%)
Alive	86	82
Dead	15	14.28
NA(Stillbirths + neonatal death)	4	3.8

The number of **preterm babies** born in cases of GTN was – 9. Preeclampsia cases were – 15, and eclampsia cases were – 7; the number of **term babies** born in cases of GTN-35 and severe preeclampsia cases was – 24 and eclampsia cases were – 14.

The total number of normal babies without any complications was 61, in which cases of GTN – 32, PE – 18, E – 10 and SPE were 1 (1.67 %). Total number of IUGR cases in relation to different types of hypertensive cases – in which case of PE – 13, GTN – 8 and E – 8.

The table shows the number of early neonatal deaths in cases of preeclampsia was – 1 and eclampsia was – 3. IUDs in cases of GTN were – 4 cases, preeclampsia was – 10 cases and eclampsia was – 1 (Table 9).

- When no treatment was given, normal babies delivered were 1.
- When tab. Labetalol was used alone. Normally delivered babies were – 44, and IUGR babies delivered were – 11 and hypoxia – 3, Meconium Aspiration syndrome – 2.

Table 9
Showing maturity and diagnosis (cross-tabulation)

Maturity	GTN	SPE	PE	E	Total (%)
Term	35	1	24	14	74
Preterm	9	0	15	7	31
Fetal complications					
Hypoxia	2	0	6	1	9
IUGR	8	0	13	8	29
MAS	2	0	2	2	2
Normal	32	1	18	10	61
Perinatal mortality					
EN	0	0	1	3	4
IUD	4	0	10	1	15
NA	40	1	27	17	86

– When tab. Labetalol and MgSO₄ (Pritchard) were used together, the number of normal babies delivered was – 13, and IUGR babies delivered was – 17, the number of babies delivered with hypoxia was – 4, the number of babies delivered with MAS – 2.

– When tab Nifedipine alone used – number of normal babies – 1 and the number of IUGR babies – 1, the number of babies delivered with Hypoxia – 2, and MAS – 2.

– When MgSO₄ (Pritchard) with Nifedipine was used together – the number of normal babies delivered – was 2 (**Table 10**).

Table 10
Showing Treatment and foetal Complication (Cross-tabulation)

Method of treatment	Normal	IUGR	hypoxia	MAS	Total
No Treatment	1	0	0	0	1
Labetalol (L)	44	11	3	2	62
Labetalol+MgSO ₄ (LM)	13	17	4	2	36
Labetalol+Nifedipine (MN)	0	0	0	0	1
MgSO ₄ with Nifedipine (MN)	2	0	0	0	2
Nifedipine (N)	1	1	2	2	3

– The table shows the number of early neonatal deaths in cases of preeclampsia was – 1 and eclampsia was – 3.

– IUD's in cases of GTN were – 4 cases, preeclampsia was – 10 cases and eclampsia was – 1 (**Table 11**).

Table 11
Showing mortality and diagnosis (Cross Tabulation Method)

Perinatal mortality	GTN	SPE	PE	E	Total
EN	0	0	1 (25 %)	3 (75 %)	4 (3.8 %)
IUD	4 (26.7 %)	0	10 (66.7 %)	1 (6.6 %)	15 (14.2 %)
NA	40 (46.5 %)	1 (1.1. %)	28 (32.5 %)	17 (19.7 %)	(81.9 %)

– When tab. Labetalol was used, IUDs were observed 6 times. When tab. Labetalol Plus MgSO₄ was used together, IUDs were observed in 6 cases, and EN was observed 4 times.

– When tab. Labetalol Plus Nifedipine was used, IUDs were observed 1 time. When tab. Nifedipine was used, IUDs were observed 2 times.

- Overall, IUD and early neonatal death-related MgSO₄ (Pritchard) were used IUDS were observed in 6 cases.
- Early neonatal deaths were observed 4 times (**Table 12**).

Table 12
Showing treatment and foetal complication

Treatment	EN	IUD	NA	Total
Labetalol (L)	0	6	56	62
Labetalol+MgSO ₄ (LM)	4	6	26	36
Labetalol+Nifedipine (MN)	0	1	0	1
MgSO ₄ with Nifedipine (MN)	0	0	2	2
Nifedipine (N)	0	2	1	1
No Treatment	0	0	1	1

4. Discussion

Hypertensive disorder in pregnancy is a common condition which is responsible for the majority of maternal and foetal morbidity and mortality. The incidence of hypertensive disorder in pregnancy (especially preeclampsia and eclampsia) and the total number of deaths from the same have come down dramatically in developed countries. This is totally attributed to improvements in prenatal care and management. However, in developing countries, it still stands as one of the major complications of pregnancy.

In this study, the overall incidence of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy was 8 %. According to Shrish N Daftaray et al. [4], it is 10–15 %. Incidence in this study is on the lower side, which may be attributed to the fact that the number of booked cases was more compared to other studies (Booked: Unbooked \cong 76:29), and patients had received adequate ante-natal care. The incidence of hypertension in pregnancy in the western population is also almost similar to the present study, i.e., according to Chesley, it is 6–10 %, as reported by Burrows and Burrows.

The incidence of gestational hypertension in this study was 3.4 %, and according to the study by Martin and colleagues (National Center for Health Statistics 2002) incidence of Gestational hypertension was 3.7 % which is quite similar to this present study. The incidence of preeclampsia alone in this study was 4.9 %. Similar incidences were reported by the following authors/workers as Williams obstetrics newer edition [5] is 5 %. According to S. Chhabra et al. [6] incidence of PE was 5.2 %. According to Lisonkova S et al. [7] incidence of PE was 6.4 %. The incidence of eclampsia in this study was 0.2 %. Similar incidence was found in the following studies as S. Samal et al. [8] is 24–1.45 %, P .N. Nabis 1.85 % [9], Aagaard et al. (2005) [10] (USA) – 0.1 %. So in the present study, the incidence is similar to the above studies. The Present study was carried out on 105 cases of pregnancy-induced hypertension (Gestational Hypertension, Preeclampsia and eclampsia) admitted to RIMS Hospital Kadapa from December 2013 to March 31st, 2016 were taken in this study.

So, severe preeclampsia cases (1) were among all the hypertensive cases (105) and, eclampsia cases were minimum (21) & GHTN had maximum cases: 44.

Socio-economic status: in this study, most of the women (74 %) had come from low socio-economic status. All patients with eclampsia were from low socio-economic status.

According to studies, the majority of the patients belonged to the low socio-economic status, which is largely related to health consciousness and the health and family welfare of the people [11]. This indicates that socio-economic status, poor nutrition and inadequate antenatal care have a close relationship with preeclampsia and eclampsia. The socio-economic status in this study was high in low socio-economic status, which is similar to other studies due to poor access to antenatal care. Due to illiteracy, they come to the hospital only in cases of serious problems, preeclampsia. Remains asymptomatic and remits spontaneously since diagnosis of preeclampsia is missed.

In the present study majority of the patients were from low socio-economic status, i.e., 72 cases (68.6 %) than middle classes cases 33 (31.43 %). In the present study, unbooked cases 29 (27.61 %) were less than the number of booked cases, 76 (72.38 %). In the study by Edgar M

Ndaboine et al. [9] in an African journal was 4 % in 201. This may be the reason for the lower incidence of preeclampsia & eclampsia in this study as unbooked cases were fewer compared to other recent studies. For patients diagnosed to have eclampsia, a maximum of patients were unbooked. 82.3 % of patients did not have regular ANC's. It has been universally accepted that adequate standard antenatal care has immense value in reducing the incidence of preeclampsia and eclampsia through its early detection and its prompt management.

Maternal age Parity and Gestational age - In this study, 66.67 % were in the age group of 18–25 years with 70 women. In this study, a notable fact was – primigravidas were 51 (48.57 %) less compared to multigravidas were 54 (51.43 %). Some recent studies have shown similar trends, but more studies are required to substantiate them. Though the number of cases was more among multi-gravida, maternal complications were high in young primigravida and elderly primigravida. According to Edgar M Ndaboine et al. [9] 2012, the gestational age was < 37 weeks, were 49 (64.5 %) cases.

In the present study, gestational age in 28-32 weeks is 14 cases (13.33 %), 33-36 weeks is 17 cases (16.19 %), and 37–41 weeks are 74 (70.48 %) cases. So this study is similar to the study by Jean Dupont et al in the open journal of obstetrics&gynaecology2015 \geq 37 weeks is 55 cases (51.4 %). Samal S and Gupta U [8] reported in their study which showed gestational age $>$ 35 weeks at 45 %, mean gestational age was 34.2 weeks (range 22–43 weeks).

The study of parity in the study by Mehul T Parmer et al. [12] primi 55 patients multi 45 patients. Most of the cases are in the age group 18–25, probably dealing with women from rural south India, where early marriage is common; primis are more affected due to early marriage, lack of health awareness & lack of antenatal care.

In this study, severe cases with systolic BP \geq 160 were 17 (16.19 %), and diastolic blood pressure of greater than 110 mmHg was 8 (7.62 %). Mild cases with a systolic blood pressure of 140 mmHg to 160 mmHg were 84 cases (80 %), and diastolic blood pressure 90–109 mmHg were 97 cases (94.3 %). Systolic BP $>$ 140 mmHg was 4 cases & diastolic BP $<$ 90 mmHg is 1 case.

Cases with hypertensive pts are 18 (56.3 %), normotensive are 14 (43.7 %), mild PIH 45 (60 %), and severe PIH 30 (40 %) by Bączkowska M et al. [13] 2014 which is similar to the present study. The incidence of abruptio, PPH, and PPE are due to severe hypertension.

In this study, severe proteinuria (Dipstick method – 3+ or more) was found in 1 case (0.95 %), Dipstick method –2 + were found in 44 (41.90 %) cases & Dipstick method –1 + were found in 12 (11.43 %) cases & – Nil were found in 44 (41.90 %) cases. Dipstick method-Trace was found in 4 (3.80 %) cases. Proteinuria is usually a late development in the course of preeclampsia. In this study, maximum perinatal mortality was found when the blood pressure was above 160/110 mmHg, and proteinuria was 3+ and above. All the maternal mortality (2 cases) had BP of more than 150/90 mmHg; and proteinuria of 3+ or more.

The study of proteinuria by Mehul T Parmer et al. [12] was mild 74, moderate 26, proteinuria in the present study was less compared to other studies due to prompt early recognition & management so that complications reduced Severity of Renal Function 'In the study Renal Function Test were Normal, and Liver function test was increased overall in 3 case (2.86 %). All hypertensive cases which were complicated by HELLP syndrome (9 cases) had overall increased Liver function test (3) and decreased platelet count (9). The Study Renal Function Test published in South Asian Federation of Obstetrics and Gynaceology, 2009 [14] is blood urea: \geq 40mg is 45 %: Serum creatine \geq 1 mg is 27 %: Oliguria: 9 %. Renal function test normal than studies due to early recognition and management. The Study Liver Function published in South Asian Federation of Obstetrics and Gynaceology, 2009 is: SGOT: $>$ 100 IU is 20 %; SGPT $>$ 100 IU is 20 %. Alkaline Phosphatase $>$ 40 IU is 34 %. LFT was 3 times the normal in study by Jean Dupont et al in open journal of obstetrics and gynaecology, 2015; Liver function test raised is less than other studies due to adequate treatment [15].

In this study, 1 case (0.95 %) did not receive treatment. The total number of babies born in this group (no treatment) is 1. Mild cases of preeclampsia usually do not require any anti-hypertensives Abha Singh (2003) [16].

In this study, Labetalol alone or Labetalol and Nifedipine combination was started only when diastolic blood pressure was greater than 110 mmHg, and systolic blood pressure was more than 160 mmHg. As recommended by the working group «National High Blood Pressure Education

Programme – 2000 [17] – indication of Anti-hypertensive agents is – systolic BP > 160 mmHg and diastolic BP more than 105 mmHg. Labetalol was the drug predominantly used in this study. Nifedipine (as the second drug) was added only when BP was not controlled with labetalol. Labetalol alone was used in 62 cases – 44 babies were born without any complication; 11 babies were born with IUGR, 3 with hypoxia, 2 with birth asphyxia & 2 with meconium aspiration. Labetalol and Nifedipine were used together in 1 case (All severe cases and cases of uncontrolled BP). A number of babies born with birth asphyxia is 1.

As an anticonvulsant magnesium sulphate ($MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$) was used in all cases of severe preeclampsia and eclampsia. Pritchard Regime was followed for all the cases – 38 cases (35.2 %). The total number of babies born normally without any complication were – 61. The total number of IUGR babies born were 29. The overall perinatal mortality was 19 in cases where $MgSO_4$ (Pritchard Regime) was used, out of which the number of IUD's was 15 and early neonatal deaths were 2 and stillbirth were 2 cases.

The overall perinatal mortality was found to be 21.87 % – Samal S, Gupta U (2001) [8] & Demise reported 18.2 % perinatal deaths with $MgSO_4$. The ETCG trial (1995) gave a perinatal death rate of 25.0 %. In the present study 38 cases where Pritchard was used. The perinatal mortality and morbidity is less compared to the studies due to labetalol and nifedipine are safe and effective drugs.

In this present series number of vaginal deliveries, 39 (37.1 %), was less than the number of caesarean deliveries 65 (63.68 %). Among the vaginal deliveries, outlet forceps were applied in 4 cases. Induction of labour by misoprostol 29 (27.62 %) VBAC : 1 (0.95 %), NVD : 5 (4.76 %) and LSCS incidence in the present study was similar to recent studies as indicated for obstetric indication.

In this study, there was not much difference between the duration of labour in relation to maternal morbidity and mortality. In cases of caesarean deliveries (65 cases) So, the percentage of vaginal deliveries was found to be more than in the above studies.

The total number of preterm deliveries were 30 (28.57 %) in this study. This clearly proves that the severity of the disease is directly related to the maturity of the baby. The disparity between the results may be due to the severity of the disease, early induction of labour and because of unbooked cases that came late in pregnancy. The maturity of the baby in this study was preterm 30, and term babies are 74, which is similar to the study of Doddamani et al [17] as a result Perinatal mortality is reduced. 38 out of 105 cases in this study had Apgar ≤ 6 (36.19 %) and APGAR ≥ 8 has 50 (47.62) cases out of 105 cases. Apgar score at 5 min in the study by Edgar M N daboine et al. [9] <7 was 17 (23.6) ≥ 7 is 55 (76.4), Apgar score <7 at ≥ 28 wks is 22.4 %, at 28–33 wks 32.5 %, ≥ 34 weeks is 16.4 % in the study.

The present study is similar to the study of J.D.K.Ngowa et al. [18] but more than Edgar M Ndaboine et al. [9] due to lack of regular antenatal checkups, complicated cases of preeclampsia, lack of awareness regarding the significance of symptoms like decreased foetal movements, late arrival at the hospital.

The study of birth weight of babies in the present study is less compared to the studies conducted by Doddamani and Edgar M Ndaboine [9] due to young primigravida, lack of antenatal care, come from low socio-economic status and lack of adequate calorie nutrition.

IUGR was the commonest complication totalling up to 29 cases (28 %). IUGR cases were most common in severe preeclampsia, i.e., 36 (39.45 %), 43 (39.45 %) babies needed NICU admission, out of which 23 babies needed ventilator support. Foetal complications in the present study are less compared to the studies due to prompt recognition and adequate treatment.

The present study was less compared to the study conducted by J. D. K Ngowa et al. [18] due to effective neonatal care in NICU with good backup by efficient paediatricians bringing out better foetal outcomes. All patients who were diagnosed to have preeclampsia before 34 weeks had the worst prognosis. The incidence of perinatal mortality due to eclampsia was 9–23 % in the study conducted by COG.

The total number of intra-uterine deaths in this study was – 15, and the total number of early neonatal death was 2, stillbirths were 2 cases, and total perinatal mortality in this study was 19. In the study by Shanti Yadav (1997) incidence of perinatal mortality was 13.4 %. Perinatal mortality study conducted by Edgar.M Ndaboine [9] 20.7 % [2012] Perinatal mortality study conducted by J. D. K Ngowa et al. [18] was 55.6 % in the year 2015.

The total number of HELLP syndrome in this present study was 9 cases giving an incidence of 8.57 %. Other complications which were encountered in the study were post-partum haemorrhage (4 cases); and (abruptio placentae 7 cases). Post-partum eclampsia was observed in 3 cases which were very low compared to other studies.

So early detection of signs of HELLP syndromes will reduce maternal and perinatal complications. The incidence of maternal complications is higher due to unbooked cases, lack of awareness and women coming to the hospital at a later stage, unable to afford the cost of proper health care; some people mistrust expert medical care and are reluctant to use it even when available. These are the ones that developed complications.

Maternal mortality: There were 2 maternal deaths, 1 due to DIC and 1 case due to pulmonary oedema. So the incidence of maternal mortality in this study was 1.8 %. In this study, maternal mortality was 1.8 % only, which can be attributed to the increase number of booked cases compared to other studies where high-risk patients were detected early and prompt management was done.

The high maternal mortality rate in countries with limited resources be understood in the context of 3 delays model. They are delay in seeking Medical care, delays in arrival & the delay in receiving standard care at healthcare facilities. So preeclampsia and eclampsia tend to threaten maternal health and foetal viability, adding to maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality. There is a high frequency of preeclampsia and eclampsia in our setting in the consequences of preeclampsia for neonatal morbidity and mortality or alarmingly high. There is a need for patients' education in recognising the warning symptoms of severe preeclampsia before the intrauterine demise of the foetus occurs or the mother develops 1 of the grave complications Antenatal care treatment of anaemia and educating the women on the significance of symptoms will go a long way in improving maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. There is no added advantage of the elective caesarean section, but the presence of NICU effective neonatal care will improve the foetal outcome. Reversing the present trend in maternal health-seeking behaviour is, therefore an issue that needs to be effectively addressed if significant improvement in maternal health is to be achieved.

Limitations of the study: sample size is limited, and most frequent complications and organ dysfunctions related to preeclampsia and eclampsia were monitored.

Prospects for further research: Future studies should validate the scoring system among patients with severe obstetric morbidity in the setting. In addition, studies should evaluate and validate risk prediction models for adverse outcomes and prognostic factors using morbidity indices and scores.

5. Conclusions

The present study is undertaken to analyse the cases of preeclampsia and eclampsia, including consequences in relation to preterm delivery, IUGR, IUD/stillbirth and for the evaluation of safe motherhood program at the population level. This study was carried out to analyse the Incidence of Preeclampsia and Eclampsia situation of hypertensive disorders complicating frequency in relation to preterm delivery, IUGR and stillbirth/IUD and early neonatal deaths. And for the evaluation of safe motherhood programs at the population level & the study carried out on Perinatal and Maternal mortality and morbidity.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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